

ASSESSING THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVE COMPETENCIES OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Annotation Experimental work was carried out during the 2019-2022 academic years, and 728 respondents were involved. The main experimental work of the research was carried out in three stages at Nizamiy Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Andijan State University and Termiz State Pedagogical Institute.

Key words: experiment, cognitive, future teachers, scientific works.

1. Pedagogical activity aimed at determining the level of development of methodological competence was organized in the process of training future mathematics teachers at the foundational experience stage based on an innovative approach. Students' educational activities were observed, interviews and questionnaires were conducted with them. Scientific works of leading scientists and experienced pedagogues on the research topic were analyzed. On the basis of the innovative approach, based on the characteristics of the development of methodological competence, appropriate problem situations, tasks and methods, forms and means of their implementation were determined.
2. At the stage of formative experience, the recommended instructions, guidelines, methodical developments and practical-methodical activity determining the methodical competence of future teachers were organized. Skills and competencies, methodical competence were formed based on the innovative approach with the help of pedagogical monitoring of students' activities, organization of practical trainings with their participation, interviews, questionnaires and practical methods aimed at

independent work. The level of development of methodical competence among students based on an innovative approach was analyzed.

3. The level of development of methodological competence of undergraduate teachers in the field of mathematics teaching methodology was analyzed based on the innovative approach of independent-innovative work tasks and the effectiveness of the used methodology, as well as their the level of development of methodical competence was determined based on the innovative approach.

It was determined that the success of experimental work depends on the following objective and subjective factors:

- creation of pedagogical conditions aimed at developing methodological competence of mathematics teachers based on an innovative approach;
- availability of sufficient material and technical base in higher education institutions;
- effective use of modern didactic, technical tools and information technologies in the educational process;
- paying special attention to the development of professional and pedagogical creativity of mathematics teachers based on an innovative approach;
- attracting qualified pedagogues to develop methodical competence in students;
- opportunities for students to use electronic information and educational resources, etc.

Experimental-testing works for three academic years, i.e. Phase I - 2019-2020, During the II stage - 2020-2021, III stage - 2021-2022 academic years, pedagogical experimental work was carried out in the teaching of "Mathematics Teaching Methodology" in groups and in the process of qualified pedagogical practice, and in

three stages and three educational a comparative comparison was made based on the average arithmetic values of the results obtained in the institution.

Quantitative data on qualified pedagogical practice and "Mathematics teaching methodology" for each stage were obtained, the results were analyzed mathematically and statistically, and conclusions were drawn using the Student criterion.

Reproductive - is determined by the low level of understanding of the planned tasks, that is, knowledge, concepts, laws and formulas, and the ability to perform independent work in the audience under the guidance of the teacher.

The level of development of methodological competence of students based on an innovative approach in the subject "Methodology of teaching mathematics".

Based on the analysis of the obtained results, we divided students' development of methodical competence into four levels based on the innovative approach (Table 2).

Productive - based on the acquired knowledge of students, it is determined by the competencies of being able to perform unusual tasks in pedagogical-technological activities and to independently perform previously performed actions outside the audience.

Competences of being able to solve non-standard problem situations and to transfer the previously mastered material to a secondary situation are taken into account. This includes course work, report, essay writing, case study, etc.

Creative - ability to perform creative tasks and acting on the basis of an example, acquisition of new knowledge and independent learning competencies are taken into account.

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